

List of reagents

Reagent	Composition	Catalog#
PBSL	Phosphate Buffered Saline without Ca ²⁺ and Mg ²⁺	Internal production, IZSLER
DMEM/F12	DMEM	Internal production, IZSLER
	Ham's F12	Internal production, IZSLER
FBS	Fetal Bovine Serum	
TrypLE™	TryPLE Express Enzyme	ThermoFisher # 2605010
Geltrex™	LDVE-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix	ThermoFisher #A1413202
Complete Medium (CM)	IntestiCult Organoid Growth Medium™ (Mouse)	STEMCELL Technologies #6005
	Y-27632 (10 µM)	Selleckchem #S1049
	A83-01 (500 nM)	MedChem Express #HY-10432A
	SB202190 (10 µM)	MedChem Express #HY-10295
	CHIR99021 (2.5 µM)	Selleckchem #S2924
	Nicotinamide (10 mM)	MedChem Express #HY-B0150
	Primocin (100 µg/mL)	InVivo Gen #ant-pm-05
Dissociation Reagent	EDTA (20 mM)	Sigma #4005-OP
	PBSL	Internal production, IZSLER
	Y-27632 (5 µM)	Selleckchem #S1049
	Antibiotics mix (pennicillin/streptomycin/fungizone)	Internal production, IZSLER
2D permeabilization Buffer	0.3% triton X-100	Sigma #X100-500ML
	PBSL	Internal production, IZSLER
Washing Buffer (WB)	0.1% tween-20	Sigma #P1379-250ML
	PBSL	Internal production, IZSLER
2D Blocking Buffer	3% Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA)	Sigma #A9418
	PBSL	Internal production, IZSLER
2D AB diluent Buffer	1% BSA	Sigma #A9418
	0.1% triton-X-100	Sigma #X100-500ML
	PBSL	Internal production, IZSLER
3D Permeabilization/BlockingBuffer (3D P/BB)	5% goat serum	Abcam #ab7481
	0.5% triton X-100	Sigma #X100-500ML

	PBSL	Internal production, IZSLER
DAPI	1:10000	Abcam #ab228549
Mouse anti-ZO1 MAB	1:100	Thermofisher #339100
Mouse anti-villin antibody	1:500	Santa Cruz # SC-58897
Rabbit anti-Lysozyme antibody	1:100	ThermoFisher #PA5-16668
Rabbit anti-Sox9 antibody	1:1000	Merck Millipore#AB5535
Rabbit anti-SP-1 Chromogranin A antibody	1:500	ImmunoStar #20086
Rabbit anti-Muc2 antibody	1:100	Abcam #ab76774
Goat anti-mouse alexa Fluor 555	1:400	Abcam #ab150118
Goat anti-rabbit alexa Fluor 488	1:400	Abcam #ab150081